

Report on Zoonoses, Alimentary and Water-Borne Infections in the Slovak Republic for 2023

1. *Salmonella* spp.

Salmonella has been an important zoonotic pathogen for both humans and animals for a long time. Disease symptoms include nausea, diarrhoea, fever and abdominal cramps 12 to 72 hours after the onset of infection. Symptoms usually last from 4 to 7 days. The main sources of disease are eggs and undercooked or recontaminated food products of animal origin, especially poultry. As reptile and exotic animal keeping becomes more widespread, so does the risk of salmonellosis caused by the rare serovars *Salmonella* spp. In 2022, 65,208 people contracted the disease in European Union countries and 81 cases resulted in death.

In 2023, 4,084 cases of salmonellosis were reported in Slovakia, with an incidence 9% higher than in 2022 and 16% lower than the five-year average. Cases were reported in all regions, with the highest morbidity being in the Prešov, Košice and Žilina regions. There were 116 outbreaks, 16 of which were of a larger size. In 100 cases of the epidemics these were family outbreaks, with between two and four cases per family. The most common aetiology of the disease and the outbreaks was *S. Enteritidis*.

Výskyt salmonelóz (A02, A02.0, A02.1, A02.2, A02.8, A02.9) v SR v r. 2023

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Fig. 1 Incidence of salmonellosis by districts in Slovakia in 2023

In 2023, the inspection authorities tested 11,446 food samples, of which 0.54% were positive, compared to 0.46% in the previous year. Higher percentages of positive samples were found in unspecified poultry (13%), broiler meat (*Gallus gallus*) (6.12%) and eggs (5.38%). Ice cream and frozen desserts, raw fruit, catering food, baby and infant food, food supplements, confectionery, breast milk and seed sprouts, soups, broths and sauces, cereals and bakery products, herbs and spices as well as beverages and teas were free from *Salmonella* spp. Seven serotypes were identified in food, the most frequently isolated types being *S. Enteritidis* with a 32.3% share, *S. infantis* with a 32.3% share and *S. Newport* with 24.2% positivity.

During 2023, 8,148 clinical samples from animals were tested for the presence of *Salmonella* spp. A total of 6,331 poultry flocks were examined, and 1.3% of them tested positive. The predominant serovar was *Salmonella* *Infantis* (50 x), followed by *S. Enteritidis* (25 x). In livestock, 251 samples from cattle were examined, with a finding of *Salmonella* in 0.8% of cases. In sheep, 3.9% out of the 76 samples examined were found to be positive for *Salmonella*. In pigs, 4.4% of 207 samples examined were found to contain *Salmonella*. In horses, one of the 27 samples tested was found to be positive for *Salmonella*, and no positive results were found in 20 samples tested from goats and two samples from deer (roe deer). In the pet group, canine examinations predominated, with 1.7% out of 646 samples testing positive. In cats, 156 samples were tested, and 1.9% were found to be positive. The dominant serovar was *S. Infantis*. Among birds other than poultry, the prevalence was 2.6%. The predominant serovars were *S. Enteritidis*, *S. Typhimurium* and *S. Charlottenburg*. In the group of exotic reptiles, zoo animals – reptiles, 62.5% out of 16 examined samples were with *salmonella* findings. Thus, out of a total of 8,148 clinical samples of animals examined, 134 tested positive, representing 1.65%. The highest proportion of positive samples was in broiler poultry, namely 2.1%. The serovar *S. Infantis* dominated, followed by the serovar *S. Enteritidis*.

In 2023, a total of 863 samples of feed or compound feed were tested for the presence of *Salmonella* spp., of which four were positive. Out of 619 samples of feed of animal origin, positivity was confirmed in four samples – two serovars of *S. Typhimurium* and two serovars of *S. Infantis*. All isolates were obtained from organic fertilizers collected in biogas plants, in two cases collected by the operator, and in two cases in samples collected by authorities.

In 2023, 7,443 outdoor environmental and water samples were tested, of which 0.40% were positive for *Salmonella* spp.

In 2023, the microbial resistance profile of 51 *Salmonella* spp. isolates obtained under the national inspection programmes for *Salmonella* infections in flocks of domestic fowl (*Gallus gallus*), turkeys and laying hens and 16 isolates obtained under the process hygiene criterion 2.1.5 verification, and under the Commission Regulation (EC) No. 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs were established. No differences were found upon comparing animal and food isolates. The trend of microbial resistance in *Salmonella* spp. isolates isolated from different matrices shows a long-standing equilibrium, with a higher level of minimal inhibitory concentration for antimicrobials from the group of tetracyclines, quinolones and their derivatives. The results correlate with data from neighbouring European countries.

2. *Escherichia coli*

Escherichia (*E.*) *coli* forms the predominant component of the microbiome of the gastrointestinal tract of humans and warm-blooded animals. It colonises the gastrointestinal tract early in life and occurs predominantly as a harmless commensal. In addition to commensal types, disease-causing types of pathogenic *E. coli* are also known. For the majority of diarrhoeal *E. coli* (from English *diarrhoeagenic E. coli*, DEC) a human is a reservoir and infections occur via the faecal-oral route, which is particularly common in developing countries or in areas where sanitation is generally poor. The exception in this case is Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), which is classified as a zoonosis. Animals are the reservoir, and infection is most

commonly associated with the consumption of undercooked contaminated food, but there is also a high likelihood of infection following contact with an infected animal. STEC is characterised by production of the Shiga toxin, and the infection often causes gastroenteritis, enterocolitis, bloody diarrhoea and in some cases haemolytic-uraemic syndrome (HUS). The incubation period is 3 to 9 days. Unlike in previous years, STEC became the third most commonly reported food-borne zoonosis in the European Union and in European Economic Area (EU/EEA) countries in 2022, according to data published on the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) website. In 2022, 12 epidemics were reported in EU/EEA countries, five of which were closely related genetically, and they involved at least 11 countries with nearly 120 cases.

In 2023, 389 intestinal diseases caused by pathogenic *E. coli* were reported in the Slovak Republic; EPEC (Enteropathogenic *E. Coli*) infection was the most frequent aetiology. A total of ten cases of EPEC infections were reported as nosocomial infections. Furthermore, four cases related to an STEC infection (EHEC according to ICD 10) and three infections with other *E.coli* were reported.

The laboratories of ÚVZ SR, RÚVZ, VPÚ, ÚKSUP, FCHPT STU, VÚVH and VÚP examined a total of 41,677 samples of food, feed, fertilizers, water and the environment. Out of 2,118 food samples, the presence of *E. coli* was detected in 3.6% of them. The presence of STEC was not confirmed in any of the targeted samples. For feed and fertilisers, 24 samples out of a total of 139 were positive, representing 17.3%. Out of 16,587 samples of different water types, the presence of *E. coli* was confirmed in 5.3% of cases. From the drinking water samples tested, 2.4% did not comply with legislative requirements. The presence of *E. coli* was also examined in environmental samples, which include air, swabs, articles of common use, cosmetics, sands and others. In this group of samples, positivity was confirmed in 1.8% of all samples.

Due to microbial resistance, the resistance of *E. coli* to antibiotics was monitored in the NRL in Dolný Kubín and in the laboratory of FCHPT STU in Bratislava. While the NRL focused on the investigation of veterinary samples in accordance with Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2020/1729 of 17 November 2020 on the monitoring and reporting of microbial resistance in zoonotic and commensal bacteria and the National Action Plan on Microbial Resistance of the Slovak Republic issued by the State Veterinary and Food Administration of the Slovak Republic, the STU laboratory focused on the investigation of microbial resistance of *E. coli* in a variety of food and water samples.

3. *Yersinia* spp.

The genus *Yersinia* consists of 21 species, of which three are pathogenic for humans – *Yersinia (Y.) pestis*, which is transmitted by fleas and causes plague; *Y. pseudotuberculosis*, the aetiological factor of rodentiasis; and *Y. enterocolitica*, which mainly causes gastrointestinal disease. The main sources of risk factors for yersiniosis are raw undercooked pork, poultry or meat products, but also fresh and unpasteurised milk, infected plants, tofu, seafood and polluted water. Food can be contaminated primarily or contaminated by contact with infected surfaces and equipment. It can also be transmitted from person to person. Young children are most often affected. The bacterium causes fever, abdominal pain, diarrhoea and even arthritis. In 2020, Yersiniosis was the third-most frequently reported alimentary zoonosis in the EU, with 5,668 cases and two deaths. A total of 16 epidemics were recorded in six EU countries. The transfer factors were ready meals and fast food meat meals.

A total of 289 cases were reported in 2023, which is up 1% compared to the previous year. The highest morbidity was reported in the age categories of 0 years and from 1 to 4 years. The diseases have been reported from all regions, with the highest prevalence in the Prešov and Košice regions and the lowest prevalence in the Trnava Region. In 2023, based on the programme of the National Action Plan for Antimicrobial Resistance in the Slovak Republic,

the monitoring of *Y. enterocolitica* in refrigerated pork (129 samples) was carried out. Contamination by *Y. enterocolitica* was confirmed in 46 samples by means of cultivation examination.

A total of 40 clinical samples were tested for *Y. enterocolitica*, with only one positive finding of *Y. enterocolitica* in dog faeces and one positive finding of *Y. pseudotuberculosis* in monkey faeces. In 2023, the monitoring of *Y. enterocolitica* in porcine caeca was carried out (133 samples) based on the programme of the National Action Plan for Antimicrobial Resistance in the Slovak Republic. Contamination with *Y. enterocolitica* was confirmed in 29 samples by means cultivation examination.

4. *Cronobacter* spp.

Cronobacter spp. is a genus of gram-negative facultatively anaerobic bacteria in the *Enterobacteriaceae* family, capable of growing in a wider temperature range (5 – 47°C), in drier environment and surviving spray drying. Members of this genus cause rare but often fatal infections in infants, the most at-risk group being low-birth-weight newborns; rarely, it can also cause invasive infection in adults and the elderly patients (immunodeficient and cancer patients). The disease symptoms are irritability, jaundice, hoarse breathing, unstable body temperature and infection can even cause meningitis. Up to 50% of new-born children may die within several hours or days. The main cause is the contamination of dried infant formula.

In 2023, no cases of these diseases in humans were reported. A total of 796 samples of dried infant formula and follow-on formula were tested, and the presence of *Cronobacter* spp was not confirmed in any of the samples tested.

5. *Shigella* spp.

The *Shigella* genus consists of rod-shaped bacteria belonging to the *Enterobacteriaceae* family and the *Enterobacteriales* order, which are the aetiological agents of the alimentary disease shigellosis, and which are pathogenic both for humans and primates. Shigellae have the capacity for adherence, invasiveness, intracellular reproduction and cell-to-cell spread. The incubation period takes from oneto seven days, manifested by shivering, malaise, fever, abdominal pain, watery diarrhoea with mucus admixture. The illness may last from five to seven days. The infection is spread via the faecal-oral route, through direct contact with infected individuals, contaminated food, water or objects. Shigellae are very sensitive to both drying and common disinfectants.

In Slovakia, a long-term declining trend in the incidence of shigellosis has been observed. In 2023, a total of 229 cases were reported (prevalence of 4.21/100,000), which is a 25% increase compared to 2022 and a 48% increase compared to the five-year average. In addition, two cases of disease vector were identified. The highest age-specific morbidity was reported in the age groups of 0 years and groups from 1 to 4 years old. The highest age-specific morbidity was reported in the age group of 0 years old (morbidity rate of 64.88/100,000) and the group between 1 and 4 years old (morbidity rate of 29.91/100,000). In total, there were five epidemics (21 patients), including two major epidemics and three minor family epidemics.

In 2023, three gelatine samples were tested for *Shigella* spp. All three were negative. No water was tested for this parameter.

6. *Plesiomonas shigelloides*

The genus *Plesiomonas* is currently included in the family of *Enterobacteriaceae* and it contains only one agent, *Plesiomonas shigelloides*, which was first isolated in 1947 from human faeces as the aetiological agent of an intestinal disease. *Plesiomonas* are ubiquitous, occurring in both fresh and salt waters, with a higher incidence in tropical and subtropical climate zones. The primary reservoir is the aquatic environment, as well as soil and animals. Its clinical symptoms are fever, diarrhoea, abdominal pain, vomiting, nausea, chills and headache. The

incubation period is up to 48 hours and symptoms subside within two weeks. Infection is spread via the faecal-oral route, contaminated water, contaminated food and human-to-human transmission.

in 2023, samples of surface water and the environment were purposely screened for the presence of *Plesiomonas shigelloides*. Two strains of *Plesiomonas shigelloides* were isolated from surface water samples, and one strain from a natural swimming pool was sent for re-examination, where the presence of *Plesiomonas shigelloides* was confirmed.

7. Legionella spp.

Legionella bacteria are a part of freshwater microbial ecosystems. They live in symbiosis with other bacteria and amoebae, especially in biofilms. Good conditions for living and reproduction are also found in water piping systems (e.g. building water distribution systems, water amusement park systems). Researchers have thus far identified 61 species of legionella, 28 of which were associated with human infections. A human may contract the infection by inhalation of contaminated water aerosol, less commonly by aspiration of contaminated water. The infection may have its course as an atypical pneumonia called Legionnaires' disease, as a flu-like illness called Pontiac fever, or asymptotically. It is not human-to-human transmissible. Depending on the site of exposure, these infections may be community-associated, nosocomial or travel legionella infections. The incidence of Legionnaires' disease has been on an upward trend in EU/EEA countries since 2016, which is related to improving diagnosis and surveillance of the disease, increasing life expectancy, water system design and maintenance and climate change.

In 2023, 75 cases of Legionnaires' disease were reported (incidence 1.4/100,000), a decrease of 43% comparing to 2022. There was a 48% decrease in the number of reported cases of Pontiac fever compared to 2022 (11 vs. 21 cases). The incidence of Legionella infections in 2023 is comparable to the 2018 – 2019 period before the Covid-19 pandemic. In Slovakia, there was an increase in the incidence of Legionnaires' disease during the pandemic, while in most EU countries there was a decrease in the number of cases during this period.

A total of 878 water samples, 253 swabs from the aquatic environment and 65 air samples and swabs from air conditioning equipment were tested for the presence of Legionella in the environment. Legionella were detected in 22% of the examined samples. Epidemiological investigation for evidence of the source of infection was performed in 17 (20%) patients with Legionnaires' disease.

8. Vibrio spp.

Vibrio is a genus of bacteria that move using a whip-like appendage. As pathogens, the most severe risk is associated with *Vibrio (V.) cholerae* serotypes O1 and O139, which produce the cholera toxin and cause cholera epidemics. For the second half of 2022 and the first half of 2023, a total of 57,024 new cases and 399 deaths were reported worldwide. The countries with the highest number of illnesses are currently Afghanistan, Congo, Haiti and Ethiopia. Thanks to rigorous hygiene, there has been no endemic disease in Europe for a long time, and it occurs only as an imported infection. In 2023, cholera was reported in 29 countries worldwide, with Afghanistan, Iraq, Iran, Lebanon, Pakistan, Somalia, Sudan, Syria and Yemen the leading countries in the number of reported cases, that is, countries with current or ongoing war conflicts, where many people live in refugee camps with disastrous sanitation and drinking water shortages. Serotypes of *V. cholerae* non O1 and non O139 cause diarrhoeic diseases. People can become infected during recreational activity in water or through the food chain. The genus *Vibrio* includes another 12 species that can cause disease in humans, including *V. vulnificus*, which causes gastroenteritis, *V. parahaemolyticus*, which causes alimentary intoxication, and *V. fluvialis* and *V. furnissi*, which cause infection of skin, wounds and soft

tissues. Infection occurs when contaminated food products are ingested, especially uncooked or insufficiently cooked so-called “seafood”, which often appear as gastronomic specialities in developed countries of Europe, Asia and America.

As in previous years, no cases of cholera were reported in 2023. There was one case of middle ear infection caused by *V. alginolyticus*. No diarrhoeal diseases were caused by *Vibrio* spp.

A total of 71 samples of various foodstuffs were examined. Different types of vibrios were isolated in several samples.

Various types of vibrios were detected in surface waters used for bathing, especially from overheated waters in the summer season. The presence of *V. cholerae* non-O1/non O139, *V. alginolyticus* and *V. vulnificus* and regular detections of *V. fluvialis* and *V. furnissii* in Slovak waters are significant, as these are pathogens from coastal areas; in our area, the presence is probably related to climate warming.

9. *Aeromonas* spp.

Bacteria of the genus *Aeromonas*, grow in both aerobic and anaerobic conditions, in a temperature range from 0°C to 45°C, and live in wastewater, soil and residual organic material. They can also survive in chlorinated drinking water or colonise the intestinal tracts of various animals. The *Aeromonas* genus is considered to be a serious aetiological agent of human infections, especially for those with compromised immune systems. They cause disease by releasing a cytotoxic enterotoxin and through surface adhesion and invasion. Aeromonad-induced disease may present as a gastrointestinal or extraintestinal infection. The incubation period of gastrointestinal infections is one to two days. Sources of infection include water, soil, food, domestic and wild animals and cold-blooded animals.

In 2023, the RÚVZ institute based in Komárno confirmed aeromonads from 18 isolates, from the stool of patients with severe diarrhoeal disease and from wound swabs and rectal swabs in 18 cases. One extraintestinal infection, a wound infection caused by *Aeromonas* (*A. veronii*) of the *sobria* biovar, was also reported.

A total of 101 strains were isolated from waters, and *A. hydrophila* was identified in 25.7% of them. In 2023, 21 samples (fish, leeches, cattle organs) were examined by the VPÚ in Dolný Kubín. Eleven of 21 fish samples were positive for *Aeromonas* spp., five samples for *A. hydrophila* and four samples for *A. sobria*.

10. *Campylobacter* spp.

The genus *Campylobacter* is an aetiological agent of the intestinal infections in humans and an agent of miscarriage in livestock. Campylobacters are widespread in nature; their reservoir is the digestive tract of domestic and wild animals. The route of transmission can be faecal-oral, inter-human, sexual, by consumption of contaminated food and water. The infectious dose is relatively low. The incubation time varies from two to five days. Among the most common clinical symptoms are diarrhoea, abdominal pain, fever, headache and muscle pain and also possible vomiting.

After recovering from acute enteritis, patients may develop neurological disorders. Campylobacteriosis has been the most reported gastrointestinal disease in the EU since 2005, and since 2011 also in Slovakia.

In 2023, 5,728 patients fell ill with campylobacteriosis; the highest incidence was in the Prešov and Košice regions. Forty-seven cases were imported and four major epidemics, with number of cases between 5 and 36, and 43 minor epidemics with two to four cases were reported. *Campylobacter* (*C.*) *jejuni* was the most important contributor to diseases and epidemics.

Výskyt kampylobakterií (A04.5) v SR v r. 2023

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Fig. 2 Incidence of *Campylobacter Enteritidis* by districts in Slovakia in 2023.

Out of 651 food samples, predominantly of animal origin, the presence of *Campylobacter jejuni* (42) and *Campylobacter coli* (21) was confirmed in 63 samples of fresh broiler meat; in 41 samples of broiler meat – fresh – carcasses the presence of *Campylobacter jejuni* (33) and *Campylobacter coli* (8) were confirmed, and in two samples of pork the presence of *Campylobacter jejuni* (1) and *Campylobacter coli* (1) were confirmed. Overall, positive findings appeared in 16.3% of the total samples in food.

A total of 1,605 samples of clinical material from animals were tested for *Campylobacter* spp., approximately 14.5% of which proved to be positive. With regard to the aetiological agent in pigs, *C. coli* was predominant, accounting for up to 86% of the positive samples found. *C. jejuni* was the most common type in domestic animals, accounting for 93% and 71.4% of positive samples in cats and dogs, respectively.

Out of the *C. jejuni* and *C. coli* profiles tested, not a single isolate was resistant to chloramphenicol (with regard to the ban on its application to livestock intended for human consumption).

11. *Brucella* spp.

Bacteria from the *Brucella* genus are the cause of the zoonotic brucellosis disease. The source of infection is an infected animal or in rare cases a human, and it is transmitted through direct contact with the infectious animal, contaminated food or an inhaled aerosol. The alimentary route of infection is most often through meat, raw milk and its products. After penetrating the skin, mucous membranes or digestive tract, the *Brucella* bacteria multiply in the lymph nodes and then attack other organs through the blood circulation. The pathogenicity of these bacteria is determined by endotoxins. The clinical course is acute and chronic. It has a wide range of manifestations from a flu-like pattern, alternating periods with fever with periods without fever, causing damage to various parenchymatous organs (liver, spleen, gonads, heart, lungs) and rarely causing meningitis, encephalitis, neuritis, myelitis. In pregnant women, it

causes miscarriages. In 2020, there were 128 cases of brucellosis reported in European Union countries and two deaths. In 88% of cases, the pathogenic agent was *Brucella melitensis*. Brucellosis is still a health problem for animals and humans in southern Europe countries, which are not officially brucellosis-free. These seven countries of the European Union are Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Portugal and Spain.

In the last 10 years before 2020 a maximum of one case per year was reported in Slovakia, but in 2020 there were seven cases, in 2021 six cases and in 2022 three cases. During 2023, ten cases were reported, nine from the Banská Bystrica Region and one from the Nitra Region.

Slovakia is officially declared as being free of bovine, ovine and caprine brucellosis incidence. In order to maintain this level of status, 64,837 bovine serological tests and 11,473 ovine and caprine serological tests were carried out.

12. *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*

Anaplasma phagocytophilum is a bacteria of the order *Rickettsiales*, family *Anaplasmataceae*, which is the aetiological agent of human and animal granulocytic anaplasmosis. The primary European vector is the tick *Ixodes ricinus*. It attacks granulocytes in the host's blood and weakens the immune system. The incubation period is one to three weeks from the tick bite. The most often manifestation of infection is a non-specific flu-like illness with headache, muscle aches, sweating, weakness and fever. It can be a threat especially for chronically ill patients. In animals, it causes granulocytic anaplasmosis of dogs and horses, while in ruminants it causes tick-borne fever. The most common sources of infection are rodents, deer, roe deer, foxes, cattle, sheep, horses, dogs and other animals.

In 2023, departments of clinics for infection diseases in Slovakia reported *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* in ten cases of blood samples collected from their patients. An infection prevalence of 10.8% was reported in dogs from veterinary clinics in eastern Slovakia and in almost 2% of small mammals examined from the High Tatras National Park. In humans the overall prevalence of tick born diseases was 8%.

13. *Coxiella burnetii*

The intracellular bacterium *Coxiella burnetii* is the aetiological agent of the zoonotic disease Q fever. The bacterium can survive for a long time in the environment and is very resistant to physical and chemical stressors. The natural reservoir is a variety of domestic and wild animals; *Coxiella burnetii* usually does not cause clinical disease in animals, but it is associated with miscarriages in cattle, goats and sheep. The main source of human infection are ruminants; the infection most often occurs after inhalation of contaminated aerosol or dust, contact with infected animals and consumption of contaminated milk. The incubation period of this disease is 20 days, but only 40% of infected humans have clinical symptoms. The acute form is manifested by high fever, headache, weakness and chills, with fatal consequences in 2% of cases. The chronic form is less common and may be associated with complications such as endocarditis or hepatitis. In 2022, four deaths of people aged 35 – 70 were reported in Portugal and Spain. In 2022, in animals within the EU, the seroprevalence was reported in sheep, goats and cattle. In other domestic and wild animals, positive results were reported only in Italy.

Since the 1993 epidemic, only occasional cases of the disease have occurred in Slovakia.

During 2023, four cases of the disease were reported (morbidity rate of 0.07/100,000), while no cases were reported in 2022. The BMC Institute of Virology at the Slovak Academy of Sciences tested serum samples from 216 patients. Antibody levels to *Coxiella burnetii*, phase II, showed the presence of possible overcoming of Q fever in four patients and confirmed the presence of acute Q fever in two patients tested.

A total of 971 samples were tested from cattle, goats and sheep. Positive serological findings were found only in cattle – 1.16%. In recent times, there were positive serological findings in

goats only in 2010 and 2013 and there are no serological positive findings in sheep in the long term.

14. *Francisella tularensis*

The aetiological agent of tularaemia, a zoonosis with outbreaks in nature, is *Francisella (F.) tularensis*, a small, facultatively intracellular gram-negative bacterium. At its outbreak sites in nature, this pathogen circulates among various species of reservoir animals. Transmission can occur through direct and indirect contact with an infected animal, inhalation of contaminated dust, aerosol, ingestion of undercooked products from infected animals, contaminated water, food, ticks and stinging insects. The disease has a variable clinical picture; its symptoms include fever, headache and aching muscles and joints amongst others. The incubation period of tularaemia is 3 – 8 days. Overcoming the disease results in long-term immunity.

In 2022, the prevalence of *F. tularensis* in animals in EU countries was reported on a voluntary basis and it was recorded in Austria, Finland and Sweden. Cases in wild rabbits occurred in Austria, Finland and Sweden. Of the wild animals monitored, *F. tularensis* was also reported in squirrels in Finland and Sweden. Among domestic animals, positivity for *F. tularensis* was detected in dogs in Sweden and among zoo animals in monkeys in Austria. From countries outside the EU, tularaemia was confirmed in animals in Switzerland, in eight hares out of a total of 14 examined.

According to the latest available EU One Health Zoonosis Report 2022, published in 2023 and summarising data for 2022, a total of 620 human cases of tularaemia were confirmed across EU countries. A total of 26 EU countries reported tularaemia, with confirmed cases in 18 countries (most in Sweden and Finland). Outside the EU, Switzerland reported a total of 114 cases, and the Liechtenstein reported one human case.

The incidence of tularaemia in humans in Slovakia continues to follow a long-term downward trend. In 2023, five cases were reported (0.09/100,000 population), a decrease of 40% from the 5-year average. In contrast, according to available ECDC data, the incidence of the disease in EU and non-EU countries (Norway, Switzerland, Liechtenstein, Iceland) has neither a decreasing nor an increasing trend. In Slovakia, cases were reported from the Nitra, Trenčín and Košice regions. These cases were spread in the age categories of 1 to 4 years, 10 to 14 years, 25 to 34 years, 45 to 54 years and over 65 years. The epidemiological anamnesis included one contact with brown hare and one contact with an unspecified wild animal, and in the other cases the mechanism of transmission was unclear.

In 2023, no outbreaks of hare tularaemia were reported by the competent veterinary authorities. In 2022, two outbreaks of tularaemia in hares were reported by the competent veterinary authorities. Out of 32 blood samples of brown hare originating from hunting in six localities of three districts in the Nitra and Trnava regions, the presence of antibodies against *F. tularensis* were tested at the Veterinary Institute in Bratislava, and two samples were positive (6.25%). These were sites in the districts of Nitra and Šaľa, in both cases in the Nitra Region, a well-known endemic area in south-western Slovakia. In the previous two years, no outbreak of hare tularaemia was detected by the competent veterinary authorities in Slovakia, but the number of samples tested was low.

The results of surveillance indicate the persistence of tularaemia outbreaks in nature, with circulating *F. tularensis* in the endemic area of western Slovakia and the possibility of exposure with the risk of acquiring the infection by different transmission mechanisms also outside the endemic areas.

In view of this fact, the Information Centre for Bacteriological (Biological) and Toxin Warfare, which is established at the RÚVZ in Banská Bystrica, has started to investigate tularaemia in ticks. Cooperation has been established with the VirÚ BMC SAV (Institute of Virology), and the results will continue to be included in reports on zoonoses and will be presented at in domestic and international platforms.

15. *Leptospira* spp.

The genus *Leptospira* consists of gram-negative, spiral-shaped bacteria that cause the zoonotic disease leptospirosis, primarily affecting wild and farm animals. The most important reservoirs are rodents, cattle and pigs. Animal infections are mostly asymptomatic, though it can cause miscarriages or sterility in cattle and pigs. Infected animals, by virtue of leptospires persisting in the renal tubules, excrete these agents in the urine for months or years. Human infection occurs as a result of direct contact with an infected animal; more often it occurs indirectly, for example through water and wet soil contaminated with urine of the infected animals. Leptospiroses are a group of acute infectious diseases with a broad clinical picture; they may manifest as life-threatening hepatitis, meningitis or influenza-like illness or as an inapparent infection. The disease may be accompanied by symptoms such as fever, malaise, headache and muscle aches, diarrhoea or cough, or more severe manifestations such as pulmonary haemorrhage to respiratory failure, hepato-renal syndrome with haemorrhages or myocarditis. A severe form of the disease may result in death. Populations in developing countries are most at risk because of lower social and hygiene standards and because of the warm and humid climate suitable for leptospires to survive outside the host organism.

In 2023, four cases of human leptospirosis were reported in Slovakia (incidence 0.07/100,000). The four men – aged 10 to 19, 30 to 39, and 40 to 49 – were from the Trnava, Nitra and Košice regions. The disease occurred in the months of July to September and were manifested mainly by the icteric form with a moderately severe course. There was no leptospirosis-related deaths in 2023.

A total of 5,272 animal blood samples were tested, 2.7% of which were positive. Out of the animals tested, samples from cattle, pigs, dogs and horses were positive. The highest percentage of positivity (25%) was found in horses, but only four animals were tested. In pigs, 23 animals out of 161 (14.3%) had positive results of testing.

16. *Borrelia* spp.

Bacteria of the genus *Borrelia* are spirochetes that cause diseases in humans and animals. They are classified into three groups, depending on the disease and the vector. Bacteria in the first group causes relapsing fever and are transmitted by soft ticks or lice. The disease is manifested by chills, headache, fever, myalgias, photophobia and cough. Another group is made up of species of the complex *Borrelia burgdorferi* sensu lato, the aetiological agent of Lyme borreliosis. The vectors of this group are hard ticks. This zoonanthroponosis is manifested by multi-systemic impairment with a wide variability of clinical symptoms. The third group in the *Borrelia* genus consists of bacteria species which are phylogenetically close to those in the first group, but which are transmitted by hard ticks. The disease symptoms are fever, fatigue, joint aches and neurological symptoms.

In 2023, 2,021 cases were reported in Slovakia, which is 47% more than in 2022. Most cases were reported from the Trenčín Region. The epidemiological anamnesis included unknown (671 x), tick bite (1,036 x), insect bite (278 x) and unspecified (36x). In these cases, *Borrelia burgdorferi* (1,084 x), *Borrelia afzelii* (158 x), *Borrelia garinii* (161 x), *Borrelia species* (384 x) were laboratory-confirmed, and in the remaining cases (234 x) the aetiologic agent was not specified.

Fig. 3 The 10-year trend of Lyme borreliosis in Slovakia

In 2023, 12 blood serum samples of dogs from different parts of Slovakia were tested by ELISA screening; 11 samples were negative and the presence of IgM antibodies was detected in one sample, but with a lower titre (dubious finding).

Using RT-PCR, the Institute of Virology (VirÚ BMC SAV) examined 130 ticks sucking human blood in 2023, and 19.2% of them were positive for the presence of the borrelia DNA. Compared to previous years (27.2% positivity in 2020 and 41.4% in 2021), the reported positivity of ticks sucking human blood was comparable to the 2017 – 2019 values.

17. Chlamydia

Chlamydiae, which have a cosmopolitan geographical distribution, are among the most widespread microorganisms in nature. For humans, *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Chlamydia pneumoniae* – both primarily human pathogens – and *Chlamydia psittaci*, *Chlamydia abortus* and *Chlamydia felis* – primarily animal pathogens with a potential for transmission to humans (so-called anthroozoonoses) – are the most important in terms of a potential disease contraction. Of the zoonotic species, *Chlamydia psittaci* poses the greatest risk to humans, occurring in approximately 460 different bird species, with nine known genotypes, all of which are zoonotic and can be transmitted to humans, in whom they cause ornithosis-psittacosis. Psittacosis refers to a disease that occurs when humans are infected by parrots; ornithosis refers to transmission from other bird species, including poultry. Transmission occurs via inhalation of an infectious aerosol or by direct contact with an infected individual. *Chlamydia psittaci* causes primarily respiratory infections in humans with variable clinical symptoms. Another species of chlamydia that is zoonotic is *Chlamydia abortus*. When transmitted to humans, it poses a particular danger to pregnant women who have been in contact with sheep and other livestock. It may cause serious clinical conditions in them, including foetal miscarriage, pelvic inflammatory disease and impaired kidney function. In view of evidence and the differential diagnosis, all chlamydial infections represent a serious medical problem. Most of them do not have “typical” clinical symptoms that would allow the diagnosis to indicate the disease.

In 2023, no cases of mammal chlamydiosis or ornithosis (psittacosis) were reported in humans. This means that the trend in incidence from previous years continues, where no human cases have been reported since 2009 (with the exception of 2013 and 2015). The probable cause is the lack of differential laboratory diagnosis, as a result of which these infections may pass under a different diagnosis.

In 2023, 91 animal blood sera were tested for the presence of chlamydial antibodies, with negative results for the first time. Although testing for confirmation of chlamydiosis in animals

has become optional and is not included in the Veterinary Prevention and Protection Plan for the Territory of the Slovak Republic, it should be noted that ruminants with reproductive problems and after miscarriage (especially sheep) must be serologically tested, as in previous years. This is also suggested by the fact that between 2019 and 2022 a relatively high average seropositivity was observed in this group of animals (approx. 17%). It is therefore desirable that the animals (cattle, sheep and goats) be examined regularly when miscarriages occur. The serological examinations should be carried out in a targeted way in order to obtain evidence of specific antibodies and, in particular, to monitor their dynamics in order to identify the aetiology of reproductive disorders and other health problems. Animals should also be tested for chlamydiosis before their trade, sale, transfer and quarantine.

18. *Mycobacterium* spp.

Pathogenic species from the genus *Mycobacterium* are the aetiological agents of tuberculosis in humans and animals. Zoonotic potential comes mainly from the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex. Bacteria from a sick person or animal can be transmitted through the respiratory tract, contaminated food, direct contact with wounded skin or through the mucous membranes. Clinical signs include weakness, fatigue, lack of appetite, loss of weight, subfebrility, night sweats, muscle and joint ache, cough, later cyanosis, dyspnoea and chest pain. If the treatment of the disease is not effective, the risk of death in patients with tuberculosis will reach almost 50%. Among the EU/EEA countries, Slovakia ranks second after Iceland in success rate of the treatment. Many cases of the disease are reported in high-risk groups, such as homeless people, migrants, prisoners, ethnic minorities, persons with HIV, alcoholics, drug addicts and other marginalised groups. Cross-border migration is also a threat. Since migration is on the rise, tuberculosis will not be permanently eradicated in any country unless it is eliminated on a global scale.

Despite the rising living standards of humans, the availability of modern anti-infection treatment, awareness and education of the population, tuberculosis is still one of the most serious infectious diseases in the world. Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis is characterised by resistance to at least two essential anti-tuberculosis drugs, isoniazid and rifampicin. Until 2020, the trend in the incidence of resistant forms of tuberculosis in Slovakia had a declining character. An increase occurred in 2021 mainly due to the impact of the war in Ukraine, with the subsequent movement of migrants from a country with a high incidence of drug-resistant tuberculosis to our territory. Risk factors associated with tuberculosis are male gender, older age, substance abuse (especially smoking of tobacco and drinking of alcohol), associated diseases and socioeconomic conditions.

In 2023, the Slovak Republic also retained its status as an officially bovine tuberculosis-free country. In 2023, in the Research institute based in Zvolen, no samples from animals were examined for suspicion of tuberculosis.

Situácia TBC na Slovensku

Zdroj: NRT

Fig. 4 The TBC situation in Slovakia in the period 1960 – 2023

19. *Listeria* spp.

Listeria monocytogenes is the only pathogenic species out of the listeriae known to date, and it is the aetiological agent of the zoonotic disease listeriosis, which is characterised by a high mortality rate. Listeriae are able to multiply even when stored in a refrigerator, and they are resistant to higher concentrations of kitchen salt. In the wild, rodents are a reservoir of listeriae. The most common mode of transmission to humans is the consumption of contaminated food, especially raw or uncooked food. The disease is manifested by flu-like symptoms, including fever, muscle aches and gastrointestinal discomfort. Due to the prolonged incubation period, it is often very difficult to determine the source of infection. In 2020, there were 16 reported food-borne listeriosis outbreaks in the EU, in which 120 people became ill; the outbreaks were mainly connected to fish.

In 2023, a total of 21 cases of listeriosis were reported in Slovakia (morbidity rate of 0.39/100,000), which is four cases fewer than in 2022 and 28% higher than the five-year average. One case of neonatal (disseminated) listeriosis was reported (morbidity rate of 0.02/100,000), while in 2022 there were two cases. Most cases of listeriosis were reported in the Bratislava Region. Three cases of death caused by listeria infection were reported.

In 2023, 9,211 samples from 31 types of food were tested. The positivity rate was 0.58%. Higher percentages of positive findings were reported in raw meat. Positive findings were found in cattle (6.67%) and sheep (2.63%). A total of 2,601 swabs were tested for the presence of listeria, two of which were positive. In 2023, as in previous years, serotype 1/2a was the most frequently isolated serotype from food, accounting for 77.8%. Although serotype 1/2a is the most commonly isolated serotype from food, most human epidemics are caused by serotype 4b.

20. *Bacillus anthracis*

Bacteria of the species *Bacillus anthracis* are the aetiological agent of splenic anthrax, which is primarily a disease of ruminants but can also affect all mammals, including humans. Anthrax spores can survive in the environment for more than 100 years, making contaminated soil or

animal raw materials a permanent source of infection. The human disease varies according to the site of infection and has three main forms – skin, gastrointestinal and pulmonary. Anthrax is a rare disease in EU countries. In 2017 – 2021, EU/EEA countries reported 17 confirmed cases, from one to six per year.

In 2021, four confirmed cases of anthrax were reported, one by Bulgaria and three by Spain. Three probable cases were reported – in France (one case) and Spain (two cases). Of the 30 EU/EEA countries reporting, 27 reported zero cases. In June 2022, 100 cattle died from anthrax in Croatia and six people contracted infection.

The last case of anthrax in humans in Slovakia was reported in 2003, and in animals in 2014. Sixteen samples of raw materials from the leather industry were also tested with negative results and no *B. anthracis* spores found in any of the three suspected shipments.

21. Clostridioides spp.

The bacterial genus *Clostridium* (*Cl.*) causes various types of disease in humans and animals. The basis of its pathogenicity is the production of exotoxins. *Cl. botulinum* is the aetiological agent of botulism in humans and animals. Infection is manifested by dry mouth, paralysis of the eyes, skeletal and respiratory muscles, swallowing and speech disorder. Death comes on the 2nd to 5th day after ingestion; the mortality rate is 17 – 80%. In the past, the risks of alimentary botulism were associated with home-canned food, but nowadays industrially produced food or food prepared in restaurants has become of increasing epidemiological importance. *Cl. perfringens* is a common cause of food poisoning. The incubation period is 6 – 24 hours. The disease symptoms are cramps, diarrhoea and sometimes fever and vomiting. In animals, especially young ones, *Cl. perfringens* causes intestinal diseases. Another group are wound infections caused by several types of clostridia – *Cl. perfringens*, *Cl. septicum*, *Cl. histolyticum*, *Cl. Novyi*, *Cl. sordelli* and *Cl. tetani*.

In 2023 or in the previous year, *Cl. botulinum* (A05.1) was not an aetiological agent in Slovakia. During 2023, a total of 4,716 cases caused by *Clostridioides difficile* (A04.7) were reported (morbidity rate of 86.78/100,000), an increase by 2% compared to 2022 (when 4,603 cases were reported) and an increase by 14% compared to the five-year average. Diseases of A 04.7 type were reported from all regions, with the highest incidence in the Banská Bystrica Region (morbidity rate of 119,97/100, 000) and the lowest morbidity in the Trnava Region (morbidity rate of 62,45/100,000).

In total, 1,754 food samples were tested for *Cl. perfringens*, 0.23% of which were positive. Out of 3,435 food samples tested for *sulphite-reducing clostridia*, only one sample of ready meals was positive. A total of 1,467 samples from clinically sick or dead animals were tested for *Clostridioides* spp., and 68.6% were found positive.

Out of the 106 feed samples tested for *Clostridioides* spp., 7.5% were found to be positive, mainly in hay, haylage and silage. The bacteria *Cl. perfringens* is an indicator parameter for faecal water pollution, 791 water samples were tested for its presence. None of the bottled, spring or mineral water samples tested were positive; positive findings were found in drinking water. In total, 133 water samples were tested for *sulphite-reducing clostridia*, with positive findings in 62.4% of them; all positive findings were in surface water samples only, where 96.5% of the 86 samples tested were positive.

22. Staphylococcus aureus (coagulase-positive staphylococci and their toxins)

Staphylococcus aureus is a Gram-positive coccus bacterium that is found in more than 50% of healthy people. In addition to being an aetiological agent itself, it is also characterised by its ability to produce toxins. After consumption of food containing these toxins, an alimentary poisoning, staphylococcal enterotoxigenosis, arises. Humans are the most sensitive to their effect. The source of the disease can be all kinds of contaminated food, especially food protein-rich ready-to-eat dairy products, filled confectionery and bakery and delicatessen products. The risk

of disease from staphylococcus-contaminated food increases with time, inappropriate food storage temperature and conditions inside the food. In 2020, there were 43 epidemics in European Union countries caused by toxins produced by *Staphylococcus aureus*.

In 2023, there were 59 gastroenteritis cases caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*, all occurring within a single epidemic.

Of 9,924 food samples tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci, 1.22% exceeded the regulatory limits. Food types in which the limits were frequently exceeded were breast milk 10.29%, milk and dairy products 4.76% and delicatessen products 1.72%. Staphylococcal enterotoxin was not detected in any of the samples. The production of Enterotoxin was demonstrated in nine isolates (18.37%) from ready-to-eat meals and breast milk. Biological material from animals was examined in case of clinically ill animals, and the number of positive detections of *Staphylococcus aureus* was 14.76% out of 2,324 samples.

Out of 32,982 water and environmental swab samples, 1.33% had positive findings for *Staphylococcus aureus*, with the highest positive findings in swabs from hospital environments. Toxin-producing isolates were also found mainly in swabs from hospital environments and clinical material.

Antimicrobial resistance was monitored in 581 samples of food, animals, water and the environment, and resistance was observed in 15.32% of the samples. In food, 11.80% of the isolates were positive for methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. In 158 samples from different animal species, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* was detected in 21.52% of isolates. Resistance to methicillin was observed in 245 isolates from water and the environment, and 13.87% of the isolates were resistant; isolates from water did not show resistance.

23. *Enterococcus* spp.

Enterococcus spp. is a genus of gram-positive cocci, characterised by high resistance, containing more than 60 species, many of which belong to the normal gut microbiota of humans and animals, but some are aetiological agents of human disease. Most often they cause infections of the urogenital tract, bacteraemia, endocarditis, diverticulitis, soft tissue infections of the pelvic area and postoperative wounds. Because enterococci possess both natural and acquired resistance to antibiotics, they are important nosocomial pathogens. While *E. faecalis* is the more frequently detected species, *Enterococcus faecium* is more problematic because of its resistance, especially to vancomycin. In veterinary medicine, this trend is not yet as pronounced as in human medicine, but the incidence of urinary tract infections caused by enterococci is increasing. The presence of enterococci in water is one of the indicators of faecal contamination.

In 2023, two illnesses caused by *Enterococcus faecalis* were reported.

Out of 78 food samples analyses, 1.3% showed positivity. Out of 14,510 water samples, 7.5% were above the regulatory limit or were positive. Out of 26,067 environmental samples, *Enterococcus* spp. were detected in 19.6% of them, with most positive samples coming from objects of common use and sandboxes. Antibiotic-resistant Enterococci were present in four (30%) of the surface water samples, with resistance to ciprofloxacin predominating.

24. *Lyssavirus*

The agents of rabies are RNA viruses of the genus *Lyssavirus*. This disease affects all types of warm-blooded animals and is transmissible to humans. After penetrating the body, it spreads to the central nervous system, where it multiplies and causes inflammation of the brain, from which it later continues through nerve fibres to the salivary glands and saliva. The incubation period is 1 to 3 months. Among animals, foxes are particularly susceptible to rabies. After the onset of rabies, the mortality rate is 100%. Protective vaccination is the only effective measure.

The last rabies disease in humans in Slovakia was reported in 1990.

In 2023, 1,000 animals were tested at the NRL for rabies virus, none of which tested positive. As part of the eradication programme, 735,592 vaccination doses were laid for the oral vaccination of foxes.

25. Influenza virus

Influenza is among the oldest infectious and transmissible diseases of humans and animals; it is caused by an RNA virus. The most dangerous group are the type A influenza viruses that infect humans, several species of mammals and a wide variety birds. The genus *Influenza virus A* also includes avian influenza viruses, the reservoir of which is waterfowl. The infection causes a wide spectrum of symptoms in birds, from a mild course to a highly contagious and rapidly fatal disease. This form is also known as HPAI – *highly pathogenic avian influenza*.

In 2023, 179,944 cases of influenza and influenza-like illnesses were reported, with the highest incidence in the Trnava Region (14,685.0/100,000 individuals under the care of reporting physicians). Age-specific morbidity was the highest in the group 0 to 5-year-olds and the lowest in the group over 60. The aetiology of influenza illnesses was dominated by the influenza A virus without further specification over the influenza B virus without further specification.

The virology institute VÚ Zvolen serologically examined 1,051 blood samples from 103 poultry farms without any positive findings. Tests for the nucleic acid of avian flu virus were carried out on 52 samples from birds living in the wild and 171 samples from domestic poultry. A total of 45 samples tested positive.

26. Tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBEV)

Tick-borne encephalitis (TBE) is a disease affecting humans and warm-blooded animals. Three subtypes are known, with the European subtype being associated with a milder disease course and a mortality rate of 0.5-2%, with almost 10% of patients subsequently suffering from various neurological problems. The incubation period is 7 – 28 days. The disease takes several forms, such as: abortive, meningitic, encephalitic, encephalomyelitic and bulbo-cervical. The clinical course of the disease usually has two stages. The first phase resembles the flu and is followed by a symptom-free period lasting 1 – 20 days. Typical second-phase symptoms are headaches, photophobia, double vision and vomiting. The TBEV reservoir animals are rodents and insectivores, and ticks are the vector. TBEV can also be transmitted via the alimentary route, for example, through milk from infected animals. The best form of protection is vaccination.

In Slovakia, we have for a long time seen an increasing trend in the incidence of tick-borne encephalitis.

During 2023, 201 cases were reported, which is comparable to the previous year (205 cases) and is an increase of 25% compared to the five-year average. The highest prevalence since 2015 is reported in the Banská Bystrica and Žilina regions. The highest age-specific morbidity was in the age group of 45 to 64 years. The epidemiological anamnesis included a tick bite (85 x, 42%), unknown mechanism of transmission (48 x, 24%) and ingestion (68 x, 34%). The patient was not properly vaccinated in even a single case. Three epidemics were reported from the Banská Bystrica (two cases) and Trenčín regions (one case), with unpasteurised sheep milk and its products being the likely transmission factor in the epidemics. In 2023, two deaths in age groups 65+ and 45 to 54 were reported from the Banská Bystrica and Trenčín regions. In one case, tick bites as well as consumption of high-risk dairy products were denied; in the other case, a tick bite was reported. The patient properly vaccinated in even a single case.

Výskyt kliešťovej encefalítidy (A84.0, A84.1, A84.8) v SR v r. 2023

Zdroj údajov: EPIS, © ÚVZ SR

Fig. 5 Incidence of tick-borne encephalitis by districts in Slovakia in 2023

In 2023, 201 samples of milk and milk products were tested for TBEV, of which two were positive, representing a positivity rate of 1%. The Virology Institute in Zvolen tested two samples of horse native blood by the RT-PCR method with negative results. The Virology Institute BMC SAV examined 37 ticks parasitising on humans without positive findings.

27. West Nile virus (WNV)

The WNV is the aetiological agent of West Nile fever. Birds are the reservoir and main host of the virus, while various types of mosquitoes that suck the infected blood of birds serve as vectors. WNV is transmitted through mosquito bites. Both humans and other mammals may contract the infection, with approximately 80% of infections being asymptomatic. Approximately 20% of the WNV infections can cause West Nile fever, which in humans is manifested by headache, malaise, fever, myalgia, vomiting, rash, fatigue and eye pain. In less than one per cent of cases, a more serious form of the disease known as West Nile neuroinvasive disease, which affects the nervous system, may develop. In 2023, and as of 4 January 2024, 709 autochthonous cases of the WNV infection in humans had been reported from nine EU countries, including 67 deaths; seven EU countries have reported 153 outbreaks in equine animals and 251 outbreaks in birds. In 2023, all countries that reported outbreaks in horses and birds also reported locally acquired WNV infections in humans. The number of reported human cases is lower than in 2022, but the number of regions affected is the highest since the peak reached in 2018.

Since 2019, the first autochthonous human cases of West Nile fever have been reported in Slovakia. In 2023, no case of West Nile fever in humans were reported in Slovakia. In 2023, 62 sera from horses were examined by the institutes of the ŠVPÚ, with one positive result (ELISA IgG) from the district of Rimavská Sobota. In 2018 and 2019, the virus was confirmed

in mosquitoes in the Bratislava and Banská Bystrica regions. Mosquitoes captured in 2023 are still in the process of analysis.

28. Dengue virus

Dengue fever is caused by a virus whose vector is the mosquito *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* species. Its incubation period is 3 to 14 days. The disease may have a febrile course or it may appear as a haemorrhagic fever. In 1970, Dengue fever was an endemic in only nine countries outside Europe. In Europe, it has occurred only as a result of travel activities, but in 2012 the virus was introduced from South America to the island of Madeira, and in 2018 nine autochthonous cases of the disease were confirmed in the EU.

In 2023, six imported cases of the disease were reported (morbidity rate of 0.11/100,000), which is five more cases than the previous year. The cases of the disease that occurred in the past were all imported infections.

29. Hantaviruses

Hantaviruses cause diseases belonging to the group of haemorrhagic fevers in humans, but they are not transmissible from person to person. Their reservoir is rodents that excrete the virus in urine, stool and saliva. The most common mode of transmission to humans is inhalation of contaminated dust. In Europe, including Slovakia, there are several types of hantaviruses that cause this disease; the most common aetiological agent is the Puumala virus, which causes disease with a mild course. The Dobrava-Belgrade virus is responsible for more severe forms of the disease and can cause severe to fatal illness.

The incidence of haemorrhagic fever cases with hantavirus origin is on the rise in Slovakia. Surveillance of hantaviruses began to improve after the establishment of the NRC for hantaviruses and haemorrhagic fevers, where more cases have been reported since 2017.

In 2023, a total of 154 cases were reported (morbidity rate of 2.84/100,000), which is an 83% increase compared to the previous year. Cases were reported in all age groups, with the highest morbidity in the group of 5 – 9 year old (morbidity rate of 6.82/100,000). The disease was reported from all regions except for Bratislava and Žilina, with the highest incidence in the Prešov and Košice regions.

30. Norwalk virus

Norwalk virus, also known as the “winter vomiting virus”, is a small, highly contagious virus whose only reservoir is human beings. Transmission occurs via the faecal-oral route, as well as contaminated food and drink. The incubation period is from 12 to 72 hours; the disease is manifested by severe watery diarrhoea, vomiting, nausea, abdominal pain and high temperature, with symptoms lasting 1 to 3 days. Uncooked foods are especially risky.

In 2023, 2,882 cases of disease caused by the Norwalk virus were reported, a decrease by 14% comparing to 2022. The groups with the highest age-specific morbidity were 0-year-olds and 1-4 year old children. There were 39 outbreaks, 19 of which were of a larger size. In all, 246 cases were reported as nosocomial infections.

Twenty-four samples were tested for the presence of the virus in food, and the presence of norovirus RNA – genotype GII – was detected in one sample.

31. Rotavirus

The rotavirus is an RNA virus that mutates and recombines easily and that is stable and capable of rapid multiplication. It can survive in the air and on contaminated surfaces for several days. It is transmitted via the faecal-oral route, through consumption of contaminated food or contaminated objects. The incubation period of infection is one to three days. Early symptoms include fever, vomiting and abdominal pain. Children under the age of five are at high risk from

the disease. In Europe, the disease is most common in the autumn and winter. The best form of protection against infection is vaccination.

The rotavirus diarrhoeal diseases show a long-term increasing trend in Slovakia. In 2023, 6,738 cases were reported (morbidity rate of 123.98/100,000), which is 84% more than in the previous year. Rotaviruses caused 139 epidemics, 26 of which were major epidemics. The highest morbidity was reported in the Prešov, region and the highest age-specific morbidity was reported in children of the 0 years age group. A total of 387 cases were reported as nosocomial infections, and 38 were imported cases.

Food and water were not tested for the presence of the virus.

**Výskyt zvolenej diagnózy v SR podľa miesta nákazy
v r. 2023
Diagnóza a080**

Fig. 6 Incidence of Rotavirus Diarrhoea by Districts in Slovakia in 2023.

32. Hepatitis A virus – HAV

The hepatitis A virus (HAV) is the aetiological agent of the acute inflammatory liver disease whose main reservoir is human beings. The infection spreads via the faecal-oral route or via contaminated water and food. In 2022, 4,516 cases of HAV were reported in the EU, with the highest number of cases registered in Romania and Germany.

Since 2020 a significant decrease in HAV morbidity was observed, which is likely related to the prevention and control measures put in place to combat COVID-19. In 2023 we see a significant increase in morbidity. There were 1,907 cases of HAV reported, which is a 30.1-fold increase comparing to 2022. Epidemics of the disease were reported in the Prešov (613 cases) and Košice regions (1,209 cases), where the epidemic also continued in 2024. One death was reported in a child aged 1 – 4 years in the Michalovce District.

In 2023, no foodstuffs were tested for the presence of HAV.

33. Hepatitis E virus – HEV

Hepatitis E is an infectious viral liver disease that spreads through the faecal-oral route, contaminated water, food and transfusions. Its incubation period ranges from 14 to 70 days. The most common route of HEV transmission is the consumption of raw or undercooked pork, venison, liver or products made from them. At the World Hepatitis Day 2023, the WHO focused on the topic “One Life, One Liver” to illustrate the importance of the liver for a healthy life and the need to scale up prevention, testing and treatment of viral hepatitis to prevent liver disease, thus achieving the goal of hepatitis elimination by 2030.

HEV has been on an increasing trend in Slovakia since 2012. In 2023, 94 cases of the disease were reported in Slovakia, with the highest incidence in the Prešov and Košice regions. The highest age-specific morbidity was reported in the group of over 55 years old. One case was an imported infection from Egypt. According to an analysis of clinical samples performed by UVLF in Košice, the genotyping of clinical samples of cases in Slovakia shows the occurrence of the genotype HEV-3, which is frequently found in European countries.

In 2023, the presence of HEV RNA was not confirmed in any food and animal samples analysed.

Výskyt zvolenej diagnózy v SR podľa miesta bydliska
od 1. 1. 2023 do 31. 12. 2023
Diagnóza B172

Zdroj údajov: EPIS, © ÚVZ SR

Fig. 7 HEV incidence by districts in Slovakia in 2023

34. Enteroviruses

The genus *Enterovirus* represents a large group that includes the *Enterovirus A–D* and *Rhinovirus A–C* species and also includes medically important human pathogens, while the *Enterovirus E–L* species include enteroviruses (EVs) infecting animals. The most important serotypes of this genus are polioviruses (PV) 1–3, whose occurrence in the world is strictly monitored by WHO. Other enteroviruses, non-polio enteroviruses (NPEV), are amongst the most common human viral infections. The disease is mainly transmitted via the faecal-oral route (less often by infected aerosols), while it spreads more rapidly in closed communities (households, nurseries, hostels, shopping malls...). The virus is most often eliminated by the

host's immune system in the early stages of infection, so the disease often runs its course inapparently or with only flu-like symptoms and the body heals spontaneously. However, in some cases EV infections can have a serious, even fatal impact on the body. The severity of the disease is influenced by the patient's condition and the pathogenetic properties of the virus. The risk group includes newborns, children, the elderly and immunocompromised people. Currently, due to the large global migration of the human population, surveillance of EVs is still an important part of PV control as part of their global eradication.

The National Reference Centre for Enteric Virus Identification confirmed the enterovirus infection in one patient. The NRC for poliomyelitis confirmed the enterovirus infection in 21 samples from 11 patients. In wastewater samples, the EV was isolated in 66 samples.

In 2023, the PV was not isolated in clinical samples or waste waters.

Given the potential for global movement of travellers (including refugees and migrants) and the ongoing military conflict in Ukraine, where PV vaccination rates are below 50% in some regions, with two cases of polio and 19 contacts infected with these viruses reported from Ukraine in 2021, it is important that the surveillance system for EVs continues to be maintained.

35. Prions

The cause of transmissible, incurable and fatal prion-induced diseases in both humans and animals is the production of excessive amounts of prion protein and its subsequent transformation into a pathogenic form. The prions that cause bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE) are able to overcome the interspecies barrier and are transmitted to humans and different animal species. A new variant Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease (CJD) has emerged in humans after eating BSE-infected beef and has also been transmitted from person to person through blood transfusions. For prion disease in sheep and goats (scrapie) the transmission to humans has not been proven. In addition to the classical form of scrapie, there is also an atypical form of scrapie that is detected in Slovakia.

In 2023, the incidence of CJD was laboratory confirmed in 27 cases, representing a prevalence of 0.50/100,000. The most cases were reported in the Žilina and Banská Bystrica regions. The highest age of a patient was 77 years.

In total, 6,247 samples from cattle were tested for BSE, all of which returned negative results. The last confirmed case of BSE in Slovakia was diagnosed in 2010. A total of 13,384 samples taken from sheep and goats were tested for scrapie. All samples tested were with negative results.

Currently, the BSE situation in Slovakia is very favourable, thanks to the efforts of the competent veterinary authorities and private veterinarians, and the situation in sheep is stable, except for one case of atypical scrapie.

36. *Toxoplasma gondii*

The *Toxoplasma gondii* is an intracellular parasite capable of infecting almost all species of warm-blooded animals. Since 2016, toxoplasmosis has shown a decreasing trend in Slovakia. According to the latest scientific studies, about 20% of the human population is infected in Slovakia.

In 2023, a total of 59 cases were reported (a morbidity rate of 1.02/100,000), which is an incidence comparable to 2022 and a 25% decrease compared to the five-year average. The cases were reported from all regions except for the Bratislava Region, with the highest morbidity occurring in the Trenčín Region. In 2023, one case with vertical transmission was reported; it was an asymptomatic case of neonatal toxoplasmosis.

Food has not been tested for the presence of *Toxoplasma gondii*, and there is no legal obligation to do so, despite the fact that some meats pose a risk of contracting this parasite. In 807 samples of blood and faeces from animals examined by the ŠVPÚ and ParÚ SAV, 2.4% were positive.

37. *Plasmodium* spp.

Parasitic protozoa of the genus *Plasmodium* are the aetiological agents of malaria; their vector of transmission and definitive hosts are mosquitoes of the genus *Anopheles*, six species of which are also found in Slovakia. The first symptoms are headache, muscle pain, vomiting, followed by a malarial attack with chills, high fever and convulsions. *Plasmodium falciparum* causes the most severe clinical forms of disease, including liver and kidney failure, encephalopathy, cerebral oedema and coma. Malaria was endemic in European Union countries until the 1970s. It was eradicated in Slovakia in 1963. Currently, the disease occurs in Slovakia only as an imported disease. Around 99% of malaria cases reported each year in the EU are travel-related.

In 2023, nine imported cases were reported (morbidity rate of 0.17/100,000), while in 2022 there were two cases. The cases were imported from Tanzania (three cases), Nigeria (three cases), Ivory Coast (one case) and Uganda (two cases).

38. *Babesia* spp.

The coccidia of the *Babesia* genus are obligate unicellular parasites that attack erythrocytes and cells of the reticuloendothelial system of mammals and birds. More than 100 species of *Babesia* are known, which cause babesiosis, a disease with the character of natural focality. The natural reservoir are mostly small rodents. Human infections follow a tick infestation; the incubation time of the disease is one to six weeks, and the manifestations of the disease are similar to those of malaria, but without the symptom of periodicity.

In 2023, as in previous years, no human babesiosis was reported.

Out of the 182 animal blood samples tested, only the dog group was positive. The species *Babesia (B.) canis* was predominant in findings. In addition to *B. canis*, single and mixed infections with the species *B. gibsoni* and *B. vulpes* were also identified in dog samples. It is likely that a large number of positive findings are not registered, as the veterinary clinics do not report their diagnoses or treat dogs only for their clinical symptoms. Aside from dogs, five other blood samples from other animal species (cats and cattle) were tested, and these samples were negative.

39. *Echinococcus* spp.

Echinococcosis is a zoonotic parasitic disease caused by tapeworms of the *Echinococcus* genus. The definitive hosts of *E. granulosus* are dogs, wolves and jackals, while intermediate hosts include domestic and wild ruminants, pigs, horses and also humans. The definitive hosts of *Echinococcus multilocularis* are carnivores (in Slovakia mainly the red fox), and the intermediate hosts are mainly small mammals. Humans may be infected via contact with animals or contaminated food. The pulmonary form of the disease is manifested by coughing and weight loss; the hepatic form is manifested by an enlarged abdomen and weight loss.

In 2023 ten cases were reported, four more than in 2022. In the aetiology, *Echinococcus multilocularis* was mainly involved.

In 2023, 925,145 animals were tested for echinococcus. Only positive findings of *Echinococcus granulosus* from slaughterhouses were reported in animals examined only by adsppection, without microscopic evidence. In 2023, no foxes, which are the main reservoir of echinococci (especially *Echinococcus multilocularis*), were examined; therefore, it is not possible to assess the situation in terms of geographical distribution and determine the trend of the prevalence of this parasite in Slovakia.

40. *Taenia* spp.

Taeniasis is a parasitic disease caused by this genus of tapeworms, which colonise the intestines of vertebrates, including humans. A person becomes infected by consuming contaminated food, especially by consuming raw or undercooked meat or contaminated water.

Bovine cysticercosis is caused by the larva of the tapeworm *Taenia saginata* and porcine cysticercosis by the larva of the tapeworm *Taenia solium*, which develops in the muscles and organs of animals and grows into an adult tapeworm in the human intestine after consumption of contaminated meat by humans.

During 2023, no cases of teniasis were reported. The last two cases of teniasis after the ingestion of meat products were reported in 2018. The finding of cysticerci in slaughterhouses in pigs and cattle is rare in Slovakia; no positive findings of cysticerci in cattle or pigs were reported in 2023.

41. *Toxocara* spp.

Toxocariasis is one of the most widespread parasitic diseases of carnivores; it is caused by parasitic worms – roundworms of the *Toxocara* genus. Adult roundworms live in the small intestines of carnivores. The eggs of the parasite excreted in the droppings remain infectious for several years. In humans, larvae capable of surviving in tissues develop in the digestive tract after ingestion of the eggs, but do not mature to the adult stage. Risk factors involve close contact with dogs, cats or soil, eating raw meat and drinking untreated water.

The number of reports of human toxocariasis has risen again to 12 cases after years of low to zero cases.

In 2023, 140 persons with suspected larval toxocariasis were serologically examined for the presence of antibodies against *Toxocara* spp. at the ParÚ SAV. Antibodies were detected in two individuals (1.43%).

In 2023, 3,055 samples of faeces and intestinal contents of definitive hosts of roundworms of the *Toxocara* and *Toxascaris* genera were examined. In total, 10.61% of the samples tested were positive for the presence of roundworms and their eggs, which is only slightly higher than in the previous year. The prevalence of toxocariasis in examined animals in Slovakia has ranged from 8.6 to 12.6% over the last ten years.

42. *Trichinella* spp.

Nematodes of the *Trichinella* genus cause a serious parasitic disease – trichinosis – in animals and humans. If the disease is overcome, the symptoms disappear. The main reservoir of the parasite in Slovakia is the red fox, and it is endemic in eastern and central Slovakia. In 2022, there were 41 cases of trichinosis in EU countries, but with no reported deaths. Most cases came from Croatia, Romania and France.

During 2023, no human cases of trichinellosis were reported (as in previous years). The last clinical case of trichinellosis was reported in a man in 2017 (with a history of eating wild game sausages). At the SAV ParÚ, 150 blood sera of patients with suspected tissue helminthiasis in the differential diagnosis were examined for trichinellosis. The presence of antibodies to *Trichinella* spp. was confirmed in one person (0.67%).

In addition, 527,234 animals were tested for *Trichinella* spp., with positive larvae found in six samples from wild boar, bear, badger, polecat and raccoon dog. In 2023, no trichinella was found in foxes, but only eight animals were examined. Since 2009, farm animals have shown no positive case findings; cases are confined to wild animals. In 2023, *Trichinella pseudospiralis* was detected in one case, but *Trichinella britovi* remains the dominant species in Slovakia.

43. *Anisakis* spp.

A parasitic nematodes of marine fish, anisakids have up to three intermediate hosts. Although they rarely reach adulthood in humans and are usually spontaneously eliminated from the digestive tract within three weeks of infection, *Anisakis simplex* causes severe allergic reactions in humans. These parasites are often found in the flesh of cod, plaice, salmon, herring

and monkfish. The disease is transmitted via raw, undercooked or insufficiently frozen fish meat or shellfish.

In 2023, as in previous years, no disease caused by *Anisakis simplex* roundworms was reported in humans. Twenty-nine samples were examined for the presence of visible larvae of the family *Anisakidae*, all without positive findings of anisakids.

44. *Dirofilaria* spp.

Dirofilariasis is a disease caused by parasitic hairworms of the species *Dirofilaria* (*D.*) *immitis* and *D. repens* of the family *Onchocercidae*. The main hosts are dogs, cats and wild carnivores. Among the hosts and vectors are different species of mosquitoes. Adults of *D. immitis* are most commonly found in the cardiac atrium and ventricle, pulmonary arteries and the vena cava of the definitive host. The disease manifests itself with coughing, shortness of breath and eventually heart and kidney failure. Clinical signs depend on the amount of the parasite occurring in the host organism. The human host is non-specific; the subacute form is characterised by the formation of subcutaneous nodules on the head, eyelid, face, neck and chest. In the pulmonary form of infection, 1 to 3 cm lesions are formed in the lungs.

In 2023, two cases of human heartworm disease caused by *D. repens* were confirmed, one of which had first symptoms reported already in 2022.

Since 2005, dog blood samples have been tested for the presence of dirofilariasis. In 2023, 334 dogs were tested, with a positivity rate of 20.06%. While in previous years infections with *D. repens* were predominant, since 2022 there has been an alarming increase in the proportion of mono-infections with *D. immitis*, which can lead to heart failure in dogs and a fatal ending. The increasing proportion of *D. immitis* is evidenced not only by the increased number of findings of this species in dogs, but also by the first *D. immitis* infection in humans, which was reported in 2021.

Annex 1 – List of Cooperating Organisations

Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic – National Contact Point for Scientific and Technical Cooperation with the EFSA
National Agricultural and Food Centre – Food Research Institute
National Institute of Tuberculosis, Pulmonary Diseases and Thoracic Surgery, Vyšné Hágy
National Reference Centre for Toxoplasmosis at RÚVZ Banská Bystrica
National Reference Centre for Legionella, National Reference Centre for Viral Hepatitis,
National Reference Centre for Enteric Virus Identification LF SZU
Regional Public Health Authorities based in Banská Bystrica
Regional Public Health Authorities based in Bratislava
Regional Public Health Authorities based in Komárno
Regional Public Health Authorities based in Košice
Regional Public Health Authorities based in Nitra and the collective of laboratories of the Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic at RÚVZ Nitra
Regional Public Health Authorities based in Poprad
Regional Public Health Authorities based in Prešov
Regional Public Health Authorities based in Prievidza
Regional Public Health Authorities based in Trenčín
Regional Public Health Authorities based in Trnava
Regional Public Health Authorities based in Žilina
Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, v. v. i., in Košice
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology
Slovak Medical University in Bratislava
State Veterinary and Food Administration of the Slovak Republic
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute in Bratislava
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute in Dolný Kubín
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute in Košice
State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary Institute in Zvolen
Comenius University, Faculty of Medicine, Institute of Epidemiology, Bratislava
University of Pavol Jozef Šafárik, Institute of Epidemiology, Košice
University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice
Public Health Authority of the Slovak Republic
Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, v. v. i., in Bratislava
Water Management Research Institute, Bratislava

Annex 2 – Team of Authors

MVDr. Daniela Antolová, PhD. Institute of Parasitology SAV, v. v. i., in Košice
doc. MUDr. Mária Avdičová, PhD. (RPHA BB)
MVDr. Mariana Babinčáková (ŠVPÚ DK)
Mgr. Jana Bako (NRC for viral hepatitis LF SZU)
PhDr. Eva Barátová, MPH (RÚVZ NT)
MVDr. Marta Bedriová (ŠVPS SR)
MVDr. Girma Belay, CSc. (SZU)
RNDr. Brigita Benkőová, PhD. (NRC for viral hepatitis SZU)
RNDr. Ľudmila Bírová (RÚVZ based in Žilina)
doc. Ing. Lucia Bírošová, PhD. (FCHPT STU)
MVDr. Viliam Bizub (RÚVZ KE)
RNDr. Lucia Blaňarová, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology, SAV, v. v. i., in Košice)
MVDr. Lucia Briatková (RÚVZ PD)
prof. RNDr. Shubhada Bopegamage, CSc. (NRC for the identification of enteral viruses, LF SZU)
Mgr. Mária Borsányiová, PhD. (NRC for the identification of enteral viruses, LF SZU)
MVDr. Lenka Cabanová, PhD. (VPÚ DK)
MVDr. Ivana Cingel'ová Maruščáková, PhD. (UVLF KE)
RNDr. Marianna Cichová, PhD. (VÚVH)
MVDr. Tomáš Csank, PhD. (UVLF KE)
Mgr. Eva Čechová, PhD. (VÚ ZV)
MVDr. Zuzana Čuvalová, PhD. (VPÚ DK)
Ing. Monika Dräxlerová (ÚVZ SR)
Mgr. Gabriela Dringušová (MPRV SR)
RNDr. Milota Fatkulínová, RNDr. (RÚVZ BB)
RNDr. Miriam Filipová, PhD. (VPÚ DK)
Mgr. Lucia Fleischhackerová (RÚVZ TT)
MUDr. Mgr. Miriam Fulová, PhD. (Institute of Epidemiology LF UK)
RNDr. Ľubomíra Hajšová (RÚVZ TN)
MVDr. Barbora Hricová (ŠVPS SR)
MVDr. Gabriela Gadusová (VPÚ KE)
MUDr. Dagmar Gavačová (ÚVZ SR)
Mgr. Andrea Gažiová (ÚVZ SR)
Prof. MVDr. Monika Halánová, PhD. (Institute of Epidemiology UPJŠ LF KE)
MVDr. Anna Hanzelyová (VPÚ DK – SL Prešov)
Mgr. Peter Humaj (RÚVZ PD)
doc. MVDr. Zuzana Hurníková, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAV, v. v. i., in Košice)
doc. MVDr. Anna Jacková, PhD. (UVLF KE)
MUDr. Alžbeta Janáková (SZU in BA)
Ing. Martina Janečková (RÚVZ based in Prešov)
Ing. Veronika Janská, PhD. (VÚVH)
Iveta Jaszayová (RÚVZ KE)
Mgr. Miriam Kantíková (VPÚ DK)
MVDr. Martin Kasenčák (VPÚ DK – SL Prešov)
MVDr. Ľudmila Kazarková (VPÚ BA)
RNDr. Mária Karmažinová, PhD. MPH (RÚVZ BA)
MUDr. Jana Kerlik, PhD. (RÚVZ BB)
RNDr. Renáta Kissová, PhD. (RÚVZ BB)
MVDr. Henrieta Kocianová (RÚVZ TN)

Ing. Janka Koreňová, PhD. (NPPC – VÚP)
Mgr. Barbora Kotvasová (NRC LEG ÚVZ SR)
Collective of laboratories at regional public health authorities
Ing. Júlia Koreneková (FCHPT STU)
Ing. Daniela Korytárová (VÚ ZV)
Mgr. Martina Kotrbancová, PhD. (Institute of Epidemiology LF UK)
Filip Kováč (RÚVZ KE)
RNDr. Zuzana Kubicová (VPÚ DK)
Mgr. Lukáš Kunštek (ÚVZ SR)
RNDr. Jaroslava Kurpelová (RÚVZ TT)
MUDr. Viera Lengyelová (RÚVZ KE)
RNDr. Martina Ličková, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology BMC SAV, v. v. i., in Bratislava)
Mgr. Katarína Loziaková Peňazziová PhD. (UVLF KE)
MVDr. Miriam Maceková (VPÚ DK)
Mgr. Radoslav Makáň (RÚVZ PO)
RNDr. Lucia Maďarová, PhD. (RÚVZ BB)
Mgr. Denisa Masárová (RUVZ KN)
Mgr. Jakub Ondrej Mihale (NRC for viral hepatitis LF SZU)
Ing. Jana Minarovičová, PhD. (NPPC – VÚP)
MVDr. Martina Miterpáková, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAV, v. v. i., in Košice)
MVDr. Martin Mojžiš (ŠVPÚ DK)
Ing. Andrea Mojžišová, PhD. (VPÚ DK)
PhDr. Monika Halánová, PhD. (RÚVZ BB)
MVDr. Rastislav Odaloš (VÚ ZV)
RNDr. Ingrid Papajová, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAV, v. v. i., in Košice)
Mgr. Katarína Pastuchová (ÚVZ SR)
RNDr. Michaela Pellerová (NRC for the identification of enteral viruses LF SZU)
RNDr. Jana Perželová, PhD. (Institute of Epidemiology LF UK)
Mgr. Daniela Peterková (RÚVZ TT)
Denisa Pilková, MPH (RÚVZ PP)
Mgr. Soňa Pivka, PhD. (UVLF KE)
Ing. Marek Pondelík (ÚKSÚP BA)
Mgr. Matúš Prívvara (ÚVZ SR)
RNDr. Miloslava Prokšová, CSc. (VÚVH Bratislava)
Anna Sabolíková (RÚVZ PO)
RNDr. Petra Schusterová, PhD. (UVLF KE)
RNDr. Katarína Schwarzová, PhD. (LF SZU BA)
doc. RNDr. Milan Seman, CSc. (RÚVZ KN)
RNDr. Martin Sojka, PhD. (RÚVZ KN)
doc. MUDr. Ivan Solovič, CSc. (NRT Vyšné Hágy)
Mgr. RNDr. Jozef Strhársky, PhD., MPH (NRC for toxoplasmosis, RÚVZ BB)
MVDr. Katarína Strišková, PhD. (VPÚ BA)
Ing. Gabriela Šindlerová (RÚVZ PD)
Mgr. Eva Špitalská, PhD. (VÚ BMC SAV BA)
Barbora Štefanov (ÚVZ SR)
MVDr. Lucia Šulejová (VPÚ DK)
MVDr. Martin Tinák (VÚ ZV)
Oľga Trníková (RÚVZ TT)
Mgr. Andrea Ulehlová (RÚVZ PO)
Mgr. Daniela Valentová (VPÚ BA)
RNDr. Bronislava Vichová, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAV, v. v. i., in Košice)

Zuzana Vrbovská (RÚVZ PD)

MUDr. Vanda Výrosteková, PhD. (Institute of Epidemiology LF UK)

MVDr. Dana Zubriková, PhD. (Institute of Parasitology SAV, v. v. i. in Košice)

Annex 3 – List of Abbreviations

ARO	acute respiratory disease
BA	Bratislava
BB	Banská Bystrica
BSE	bovine spongiform encephalopathy
CJch	Creutzfeldt-Jacob Disease
ČOV	wastewater treatment plant
DK	Dolný Kubín
DSS	social care home
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EEA	European Economic Area
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EHEC	Enterohemorrhagic <i>E. coli</i>
EHP	European Economic Area
EPEC	Enteropathogenic <i>E. coli</i>
EPIS	Epidemiological information system
EREN	EFSA's Scientific Network on Sudden Risks
ES	European Community
EU	European Union
EVs	enteroviruses
FCHPT	Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology
HAV	hepatitis A virus
HD	cattle
HEV	hepatitis E virus
HFRS	Haemorrhagic fever with renal syndrome
HPAI	<i>highly pathogenic avian influenza</i>
HUS	haemolytic uremic syndrome
dis.	morbidity
CHPO	influenza-like disease
IEV	Enterovirus infection
IgG	Immunoglobulin G
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
LFUK	Faculty of Medicine of Comenius University in Bratislava
KE	Košice
KN	Komárno
KoNS	coagulase negative staphylococci
KPS	coagulase positive staphylococci
LB	Lyme borreliosis
LCH	Legionnaire's disease
LF	Faculty of Medicine
MIÚ	Microbiology Institute
MRSA	Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
unsp.	unspecified

NKB EFSA in Slovak Republic	National Contact Point for Scientific and Technical Cooperation with EFSA
NoV	Norwalk virus
NP	National Park
NPPC – VÚP	National Agricultural and Food Centre – Food Research Institute
nvCJch	new variant of Creutzfeldt-Jacob disease
NPEV	non-polio enteroviruses
NRC	National Reference Centre
NRC IEV	National Reference Centre for Enteric Virus Identification
NRC LEG	National Reference Centre for Legionella in the Environment ÚVZ SR
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
NÚDCH	National Institute of Children’s Diseases
NÚTPCHaHCH	National Institute of Tuberculosis, Pulmonary Diseases and Thoracic Surgery
ParÚ SAV	Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
PCH	prion diseases
pr.	case
PV	poliovirus
RL	reference laboratory
RNA	ribonucleic acid
RT PCR	Real time PCR – polymerase chain reaction with reverse transcription
RÚVZ	Regional Public Health Authority
SARI	Severe Acute Respiratory Infection
SAS	Slovak Academy of Sciences
SL	test laboratory
s.l.	Borrelia burgdorferi sensu lato complex
Slovak Republic	Slovak Republic
STU	Slovak University of Technology
ŠVPS SR	State Veterinary and Food Administration of the Slovak Republic
ŠVPÚ	State Veterinary and Food Institute
SZU	Slovak Medical University
TBC	tuberculosis
TBEV	tick-borne encephalitis virus
ÚE	Institute of Epidemiology
UK	Comenius University
TSE	transmissible spongiform encephalopathy
TÚV	warm utility water
UNB	University Hospital Bratislava
UNLP	Louis Pasteur University Hospital in Kosice
ÚKSÚP	Central Control and Testing Institute in Agriculture Bratislava
UVLF KE	University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice
ÚVZ SR	Public Health Authority of the Slovak Republic
VHA	hepatitis A virus

VirÚ BMC SAV	Institute of Virology, Biomedical Centre of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
VPÚ	Veterinary and Food Institute
VÚ	Veterinary Institute
VTEC/STEC	<i>E.coli</i> -producing verotoxin/Shiga toxin
VÚP	Food Research Institute
VÚVH	Water Management Research Institute
WB	Western Blot
WHO	World Health Organization
WNV	West Nile virus
ZV	Zvolen

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